

Serbian Biochemical Society
Eighth Conference
with international participation

University of Novi Sad – Rectorate Hall
16.11.2018. Novi Sad, Serbia

“Coordination in Biochemistry and Life”

Does peppermint's post distillation waste can reduce lipid peroxidation?

Katarina Jeremić^{1*}, Neda Gavarić¹, Aleksandra Nikolić², Nebojša Kladar¹, Maja Bekut¹, Nemanja Todorović¹, Biljana Božin¹

¹*Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Vojvodina Clinical Centre, Novi Sad, Serbia*

**e-mail: katarina.jeremic@mf.uns.ac.rs*

The use of medicinal herbs has been rooted in traditional medicine and pharmacy since ancient civilizations. Treatment and co-therapy with medicinal herbs successfully expands and develops nowadays. World Health Organization reported that 80% of population in developing countries uses traditional medicine and herbal remedies in primary health care. Due to the increase in consumption of dietary supplements and herbal medicinal products, there is a growing need for more rational use of plant resources. Peppermint is an aromatic plant with long tradition of medical use. This plant has numerous proven pharmacological effects - antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, spasmolytic, antioxidant. Phenol compounds are responsible for most of these effects. The official drug is *Menthae x piperitae folium* and from this drug, with different distillation techniques, an essential oil is obtained. In order to achieve a more rational use of plant material, scientists tests possibility of use of residues after the extraction of essential oil, for the isolation of other active principles¹⁻³.

Male Swiss Albino mice, six weeks old, weighing 25–35 g were used in this investigation. All efforts were made to minimize animal discomfort and the experimental procedures were approved by Ethical Committee for Animal Use in Experiments, University of Novi Sad. Standard peppermint leaf extract (Ph. Eur. IV, 2002) was prepared by maceration procedure in 45% ethanol, as a solvent during 24 h (1:10 w/v, 10 g dried leaves) at room temperature (N1). Essential oil was isolated by hydrodistillation technique (Ph. Eur. IV, 2002)⁴. The waste material, remaining after isolation, was filtered and deodorised leaves were used the preparation of N2 (45% ethanol, 24 h) and N3 (75% ethanol, 24 h). Lipid peroxidation and total protein content were determined spectrophotometrically in brain homogenate and in serum of experimental animals⁵.

Values of biochemical parameters in brain homogenate and in serum of group of experimental animals treated with selected peppermint extracts were compared with parameters in control group of animals by using Student t-test. The difference between compared groups was considered to be significant when $p < 0.05$.

By monitoring the effect on lipid peroxidation in the brain, it has been established that all three investigated extracts exhibit a protective effect in the state of induced oxidative stress

(after application of CCl₄ when compared with the group with one-time application of CCl₄), as they lead to a statistically significant decrease of LP intensity. In the serum, only the N3 extract shows a statistically significant reduction of the lipid peroxidation intensity.

Based on our results and previous investigations, we can conclude that examined waste extracts exhibit comparable antioxidant effect to officially prepared peppermint leaf extract. This waste and extracts may be used for preparation of herbal medicines or in pharmaceutical and food industry as preservatives of natural origin.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia (project OI 172058).

References

1. Djaković Sekulić T, Božin B, Smoliński A. Chemometric study of biological activities of 10 aromatic Lamiaceae species' essential oils. *J Chemometrics* 2016;30:88-196.
2. Božin B, Mimica-Dukić N, Simin N, Anackov G. Characterization of the volatile composition of essential oils of some Lamiaceae spices and the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of the entire oils. *J Agri Food Chem* 2006;54:1822-8.
3. Gavarić N, Kladar N, Mišan A, Nikolić A, Samojlik I, Mimica-Dukić N, Božin B. Postdistillation waste material of thyme (*Thymus vulgaris* L., Lamiaceae) as a potential source of biologically active compounds. *Ind Crops Prod* 2015;74:457-64.
4. European Pharmacopeia. 2002. 4th ed. Council of Europe, Strasbourg, pp. 183–4.
5. Buege AL, Aust D. Microsomal Lipid Peroxidation. In: Fleisher S, Parker L. *Methods in Enzymology*. Academic Press, New York, 1978, pp. 306-10.